

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

**D5.2 – Techniques for early risk
identification, predictions and assessment II**
WP5 AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised
Recommendations

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Scope of the document	6
1.2 Structure of the document.....	7
1.3 Relevance with other Work Packages	7
1.4 Background.....	7
1.5 Updates since D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and Assessment I”	8
2 Pre-processing of secondary data	9
2.1 Padding Interpolation.....	9
2.2 Linear Interpolation.....	9
2.3 Polynomial Interpolation.....	10
2.4 Spline Interpolation	10
3 Supervised learning in healthcare.....	12
3.1 Model evaluation workflow	13
3.2 Risk factors analysis.....	14
3.2.1 Methods based on DL.....	14
3.3 Latent features analysis.....	15
4 Unsupervised learning in Healthcare	17
4.1 Anomaly detection	18
4.2 Time series analysis	18
4.3 Artificial Intelligence techniques	19
4.4 Other techniques.....	19
5 Survival estimation.....	21
5.1 Non-Personalized	21
5.2 Personalized	21
6 Application on synthetic data	23
6.1 Simulation for synthetic data	23
6.2 Predictive modelling.....	25
6.2.1 Inputs and outcomes to predict	25
6.2.2 RF predictive model.....	25
6.2.3 Explaining model decisions	26
6.2.4 Risk assessment.....	27

- 6.3 Generative modelling 27
 - 6.3.1 Pre-processing 28
 - 6.3.2 Clustering..... 28
 - 6.3.3 Modelling clusters 29
 - 6.3.4 Assigning patients to clusters (phenotyping) 29
 - 6.3.5 Cluster validation..... 30
- 7 Initial architecture and connection to the pilot studies 34
 - 7.1 Data description 34
 - 7.2 Predictive workflow 35
 - 7.3 Model architecture 35
- 8 Conclusion 39
- Bibliography 40
- List of Acronyms 43
- Annex I: Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI 45

List of Figures

- Figure 1: Time series with missing values 9
- Figure 2: Linear Interpolation..... 10
- Figure 3: Polynomial Interpolation..... 10
- Figure 4: Spline interpolation..... 11
- Figure 5: Supervised learning workflow..... 12
- Figure 6: Long short-term memory cell architecture and operations..... 13
- Figure 7: Learning of the RF binary health outlook variation classifier..... 26
- Figure 8: SHAP analysis of decisions..... 26
- Figure 9: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the behaviour group of each person. ... 27
- Figure 10: Cluster analysis process..... 28
- Figure 11. Hierarchical clustering of the people. 29
- Figure 12: Models for the first half attributes of all 9 clusters. 30
- Figure 13: Models for the second half attributes of all 9 clusters. 31
- Figure 14: Comparison between data-driven clusters and behavioural clusters (clinicians’ classification). 31
- Figure 15: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the cluster of each person. 33
- Figure 16: The process of the collection of data and the models accompanying them 35
- Figure 17: Neural network that concatenates CNN/LSTM for streaming data and a simple MLP for clinical and retrospective data 37
- Figure 18: Neural network that concatenates multiple sub neural networks 37

Executive summary

This report summarizes the actions performed under T5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment” in this phase of the project and more specifically provides details of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and implementation techniques that are being used to perform early identification as well as predictions of Pancreatic Cancer (PC) risks in individuals. The previous version of this series of deliverables, i.e., D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I”, synthesized several AI/ML techniques that are expected to be able to identify hidden patterns and trends in given secondary clinical and streaming data. When all the data (mainly deriving from the patients e.g., questionnaires) become available in the last phase (3rd year) of the project, these techniques will be used for performing assessment of identified risks and subsequently for making predictions. In this second version of T5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment” deliverables series, i.e., D5.2 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment II”, work has been carried out to further explore the synthetic data on Section 6 which simulate the real data that will be provided later in the project. Finally, in Section 7 the initial architecture and approach of the AI models is provided a) having as a guide the synthetic data that simulate the streaming data (life habit, symptoms questionnaires and data collected from wearable devices) and b) taking into account also the prospective clinical data.

1 Introduction

Patients with Pancreatic Cancer (PC) are commonly diagnosed at late stages of the disease when curative therapy is hardly achievable which, in turn, results in low survival rates and as such PC is an important public health concern (P., O., N., + 20), (M., R., Q., 08), (C., F., D., + 15). In most cases, it takes years before a diagnosis is realized since most of the patients display non-specific symptoms during this time (O., C., G., 17). Continuous evolution related to pancreatic cancer research has been achieved (W., R., H., + 11), in the last few years, however, progress towards an early cancer diagnosis has been slow (E., R., B., + 13), (S., M., 10). The fact that population-based screening for pancreatic cancer is not feasible when considering low probability of PC (ranges between 0.03 and 0.3 % among ages of 40–59 and 80–99 respectively) (P., B., S., + 17), (C., R., S., 2019), results in a prohibitively expensive scheme (P., O., N., + 20), (S., K., C., + 19). Targeted screening, on the other hand, is a possibility. Diagnostic biomarkers (D., M., C., + 19), (S., D., J., + 14) have been identified from numerous studies, and the most promising results have been obtained using protein markers (B., Z., C., + 20), (R., M., J., + 15) either alone or in combination with the clinically established biomarker, Carbohydrate antigen 19-9 (CA19–9) (C., L., W., + 18). These studies mostly identify high-risk groups containing small numbers of people, for example, those with at least two affected first-degree relatives or individuals with known underlying gene abnormalities (L., W., C., + 14).

With the emergence of new technologies in the field of medicine, large amounts of cancer-related data have been collected and are available to the medical research community. AI/ML methods have become an increasingly popular tool for medical researchers. These methods can identify patterns and relationships among several features collected from complex datasets, while they are able to predict future outcomes of a specific cancer type.

This research work presents the AI/ML approaches that can be later employed for the objectives of the project to be realized and specifically for early risk identification and predictions. Keeping in mind that task T5.1 will further extend the models considered in T4.1 but taking also into account the real time/prospective data, we here present those techniques that have been used in other studies with similar objectives in order to prepare for the next phase of the project, when the initial prospective data and the complete prospective data will be available, after a while.

1.1 Scope of the document

The scope of this document is to summarize the work done under T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, during the first 22 months of the Task’s duration. The aim of D5.2 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment II” is to gather details of the AI algorithms and implementation techniques that will be used during the project’s lifetime, in order to enable early identification of Pancreatic Cancer based on secondary clinical and streaming data. The ultimate goal is to reveal hidden patterns and trends in streaming/prospective data, in order to make predictions and also perform assessment of identified risks. More specifically, the AI algorithms and the implementation techniques that are being realized during the iHelp project, are being described in a series of deliverables starting from the previously delivered D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I”, the current document and will be followed by one more update, i.e., D5.3 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment III”, due on M32.

1.2 Structure of the document

A brief description of every section of this deliverable follows.

- Section 1 consists of this document introduction, the connection with other WPs, the background work that is related to T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” as well as the updates since the submission of D5.1 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I”.
- Section 2 describes the preparation of the secondary data.
- Section 3 presents the supervised learning methods and algorithms that can be exploited in the context of T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”.
- Section 4 introduces the unsupervised learning methods in healthcare that could be used in the context of iHelp.
- Section 5 presents a brief overview of the survival estimation analysis and some potential algorithms to approach it.
- Section 6 presents the workflow for the learning of predictive and generative models on synthetic data through a simulator.
- Section 7 presents the initial architecture of the AI models.
- Section 8 concludes this document.
- Annex I seeks to present the applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI.

1.3 Relevance with other Work Packages

Task T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” concerns the methods and the AI techniques that will be developed during the lifecycle of the project, for the realization of the risk prediction models, taking into consideration the secondary data and thus expanding the models developed utilizing the primary data in the context of T4.1 – “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions”. It is considered a significant task for the project outcomes, however it is mainly related to WPs 3 and 4. WP3 is responsible for the mapping activities into Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource (FHIR) and the final storage of the Holistic Health Records (HHRs) into the project’s Big Data Platform. WP4 and more specifically T4.1 - “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” is directly connected to T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, since in T4.1 - “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” the AI models are first introduced and analyzed taking into account the retrospective data. Then in T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” we further analyse and redefine the AI models and techniques. Taking into consideration also the real-time/prospective data we improve the predictions and generally the outcomes of this task.

1.4 Background

Pancreatic cancer (PC) constitutes a substantial public health problem. Patients suffering from PC have very low probabilities of living more than a few years due to the difficulty of identifying this specific type of cancer early enough when the tumour is localised to the site of origin and is treatable. Therefore, the potential positive impact of being able to identify individuals at risk and prevent PC is huge. Furthermore, it is widely accepted that PC is not a good candidate for mass population-based screening due to its low incidence in the general population. As small as 10% of the patients diagnosed with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) have either a strong family history of PC, hereditary pancreatitis or a particular

genetic syndrome (P., O., N., + 20). The remaining 90% of PDAC patients are non-inherited cases who overwhelmingly display no alarm symptoms until the tumour is well-advanced. Recent studies have been conducted, mainly in identifying biomarkers for PC in the blood and urine, but these cannot be used for population-based screening as this would be prohibitively expensive and potentially harmful. Furthermore, other works in the literature have highlighted putative features associated with PC diagnosis such as jaundice, abdominal pain, back pain, gastric problems, weight loss, malaise and new-onset diabetes (S., P., N., + 12), (H., C., B., + 04).

1.5 Updates since D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and Assessment I”

This is the second report out of the three that will be reported under the task T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” and refers to the work done within the first two years of the project. At this point of time no secondary data have been provided yet since this is planned for the final phase (3rd year) of the project. Considering that, the work carried out so far involves the exploration of the synthetic data in Section 6 and an initial approach of the models that will be created in the last phase of the project. In Section 6, further research has been conducted on the synthetic data generated by the World Class Generator implemented by iSPRINT and its analysis along with the new outcomes are presented. Section 7: Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI in the previous version, D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and Assessment I” has been moved to Annex I at the end of this document. Another section has been added namely Section 7 in this version of the document, related to the “Initial architecture and connection to the pilots”. Therein, a description of the secondary and streaming data is provided and details on the time of arrival of each specific type of data is also included. Finally, a conceptual architecture of the AI model that will put together the work done under T4.1 - “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” but also the intended work for T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” is provided.

2 Pre-processing of secondary data

As with any type of real-world data, also in the case of health-related data and streaming data it is probable that a variety of factors (e.g., design, device malfunction, patient's characteristics or dropping out) will lead to missing data values. Most -if not all state-of-the-art models- that take temporal relationships into consideration operate on regularly structured time data. Therefore, there is a need to substitute these missing values and the process of filling these with suitable values is called *imputation* and specifically for time series *interpolation*. It should be noted that interpolation does not increase performance but instead allows the model to operate in situations where a reasonable percentage of missing data exists (no more than 40%). In contrary to *extrapolation*, interpolation only predicts missing values from data and not future values. The latter means that this section does not address time series prediction.

Figure 1: Time series with missing values

2.1 Padding Interpolation

The simplest solution to the problem is to assume that the missing value is the same as the last seen value. This way if a range of values are missing, they are all filled with the last observed value in the time series. This technique is referred to as *padding interpolation* and is useful in cases where we don't want to alter the data at all but still want to perform analysis on them. Even though it is obviously not an ideal option it is a quick workaround to the missing value problem and can be used as a simple solution when we just want to test the next stages of an ML pipeline.

2.2 Linear Interpolation

The simplest form of estimating the values of a time series is to suppose that they derive from the available values in a linear manner. In this case to estimate a missing value, the two closest non missing values are used to fit a line and the missing value of the point is derived by supposing that it is on the same line. Usually, the values that are missing are continuous time moments e.g., several subsequent values missing due to a device shutdown. In this case the entire range of missing values is estimated by the same line that connects the two closest available values. Even though this technique is very simple it sometimes yields results that might be just as good as mathematically advanced techniques (S., K., C., + 19).

Figure 2: Linear Interpolation

2.3 Polynomial Interpolation

Another way of interpolating is to fit a polynomial curve to the available data points and then fill the missing values according to the resulting curve. It can be said that *linear interpolation* is a special case of fitting a polynomial line of degree 1. In this case the resulting polynomial is fit to all of the available points which causes problems in big datasets. In classical techniques such as *Lagrange* and *Newton Polynomial Interpolation* (JFE, 13) the resulting polynomial might not be of high enough degree which means it will not pass from all available points or the degree of the polynomial might be too high and cause unwanted oscillations instead of following the available data points therefore increasing the error for the missing values. This is why it is not practical to be used in the case of time series and it is more practical to use techniques that focus on local points.

Figure 3: Polynomial Interpolation

2.4 Spline Interpolation

Spline interpolation is inspired by polynomial interpolation, only it fits numerous small degree polynomials from each point to the next, instead of a single large degree polynomial. This way the technique avoids

fitting too complex curves while also managing to pass through all available points therefore yielding more natural looking lines. Smoother lines also mean that the technique does not alter the frequencies of the time series too much which is important in cases where periodical phenomena are analysed or sought out.

Figure 4: Spline interpolation

3 Supervised learning in healthcare

The clinical data that will be acquired in the context of the iHelp project consist of multivariate time series observations. The secondary data that will be collected through the sensor devices fall in the context of time series observations. For each patient visit (or episode), sensor data and lab test results are recorded in the patient's Holistic Health Record (HHR). Supervised learning algorithms is a sub-branch of ML problems that relies on data where labels of the expected outcome are provided along with the feature inputs. The labels in the case of the cancer risk prediction model are the levels of the expected risk of developing that cancer i.e., low-, mid- and high-risk level.

Supervised learning techniques refer to either classification (map input to output labels) or regression (map input to a continuous output) problems. The goal is to identify relationships/correlations or reveal the hidden structure of the input clinical and non-clinical data for the correct generation of the risk level. When carrying out supervised learning, the principal circumstances are model complexity and the bias-variance trade-off.

Figure 5: Supervised learning workflow.

Commonly used supervised learning methods that are usually implemented for performance comparisons in risk prediction, include Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forests (RF), Neural Networks (NN) and Naive Bayesian (NB) methods.

Artificial Neuron Networks (ANNs) are developed by creating nodes (neurons) that weight certain features and produce an output value. By layering nodes in between, the input layer (features; cancer risk factors) and output layer (label; future cancer occurrence) and modifying the weights during learning, through a process called backpropagation, the resulting model forms a prediction for unseen data when one of the nodes in the output layer is positive. Deep Learning (DL) produces models with multiple hidden layers that can be used to quantify the complex nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is one class of DL models that take into account the temporality in a sequence of events, and hence is well-suited for modelling and predicting a disease onset based on longitudinal observations of

clinical events. Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) is among the most popular types of RNN architectures, and they have been applied to EHR data to achieve the state-of-the-art accuracy of disease predictions.

RNNs, particularly those using LSTM hidden units, are increasingly popular models for learning from sequence data. They effectively model varying length sequences and capture long range dependencies. In the context of the iHelp project we will evaluate the ability of LSTMs to recognize patterns in multivariate time series of clinical measurements. RNNs have the concept of “memory” that helps them store the states or information of previous inputs to generate the next output of the sequence, as it is shown in Figure 6. Specifically, there are operations in the LSTM cells that allows to keep or forget information while processing the time sequence. Important concepts are the cell state and the various gates. The cell state carries information throughout the processing of the sequence in a way that information from previous time steps can affect later time steps. The gates add or remove information to/from the cell state based on what information is relevant to keep or forget, as they learned during the training phase. Gates either refer to sigmoid or tanh activation functions. A sigmoid activation maps values between 0 and 1 while the tanh activation maps values between -1 and 1. Any value multiplied by 0 returns 0 so those values will be forgotten while when multiplied by 1 means that will be kept.

Figure 6: Long short-term memory cell architecture and operations.

The performance of the developed LSTM model needs to be verified against strong baselines, including both a linear classifier like a logistic regression model and a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). The baseline models will be implemented on a fixed window and using hand-engineered features. The optimization objective will be set as a combination of the loss at the final sequence step and the mean of the losses over all sequence steps. In order to address possible model overfitting, some techniques such as dropout or adjusting the number of hidden units will be applied (Z., L., K., 17).

3.1 Model evaluation workflow

The performance of prediction models can be assessed using a variety of different methods and metrics both in terms of development and the external validation of the cohorts. The iHelp pilot case studies reveal

a great opportunity to act as external validation in the cohorts. The model performance needs to be evaluated in terms of discrimination, calibration, generalizability, interpretability and clinical usefulness.

The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) metric will be measured to indicate the discrimination degree of the model, since the higher the AUC is, the better the discrimination would be. ROC curve (receiver operating characteristic curve) is a performance measurement for the classification problems at various threshold settings. ROC is a probability curve and AUC represents the degree or measure of separability. AUC reveals the models' capability of distinguishing between classes (the separability). AUC ranges in value from 0 to 1. An excellent model - whose predictions are 100% right – has AUC near to 1 which means it has a good measure of separability. A poor model has an AUC near 0 which means it has the worst measure of separability.

The calibration may be evaluated in terms of its intercept and its slope. Calibration refers to the reliability of the predicted risks, i.e., whether the predicted risks correspond to observed probabilities. In medical applications this is important because treatment decisions often rely on the estimated risk of disease. The calibration intercept is related to systematic under/over-prediction (H., H., T., 15). Values greater than 0 indicate systematic under-prediction while values less than 0 indicate systematic over-prediction. The calibration slope checks whether predicted risks are appropriately scaled with respect to each other over the entire range of predicted probabilities. Values less than 1 indicate overfitting, with predicted values that have too much variability.

3.2 Risk factors analysis

The two main methods of performing risk factor analysis, as investigated by (L., H., 14), are based either on expert knowledge or a handcrafted feature set. The models based on knowledge usually fix a small number of risk factors that are already validated by experts in a field and may lose valuable information that is underestimated by experts. On the other hand, models based on handcrafted feature sets identify risk factors by calculating their statistical significance to rank all available features according to their predictive power on a task. Such a task could be regression where models such as Linear, Poisson, Cox and Lasso regression are frequently used as the core methods, or classification where Logistic Regression Decision Trees or Random Forests. Most of these methods evaluate each feature separately and lack the ability to evaluate the relationship between features.

3.2.1 Methods based on DL

In recent years deep learning techniques have improved the state of the art in many fields such as Computer Vision (CNNs, Autoencoders), Natural Language Processing (RNNs, LSTMs) and have even been applied on healthcare datasets. However due to the large complexity of these models it is still not always clear what internal rules they have learned to achieve their performance. The concepts and knowledge they extract from input features is different according to architecture and task but understanding them usually involves visualizing the inner layer features. Authors in (S., Q., 16) describes a method that investigates the latent representation of hidden nodes and analyses the relationships between latent features and input risk factors. By manually categorising input features into similar risk factor groups, they assess each risk factor's importance by plotting the inner activation of the models by risk factor groups. By training a Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) or an Autoencoder neural network and visualizing the neuron's activations the authors see if the neurons that contribute to the output score are activated for features that concern similar risk factors. Such features are important risk factors. Similarly feature groups that don't contribute to the output score aren't considered risk factors by the model. We estimate that such a technique could be

applied if we have target features to perform supervised learning on the relevant WP data to find the most important risk factor groups.

3.2.1.1 Restricted Boltzmann Machines

RBM is a generative stochastic graphical model that is restricted to form a fully connected bipartite graph between its visible units and hidden units. The difference compared with simple feedforward neural networks is that each edge in the graph is bidirectional. RBMs are able to learn a probability distribution of the inputs and capture higher order correlations of the input units. They are used to investigate a representation of the input features using fewer hidden units to represent the problem. RBMs can be trained in supervised or unsupervised manner depending on the task. Since RBMs are bidirectional the training process is harder than simple feedforward neural networks and they need a gradient-based algorithm called *contrastive divergence* to be efficiently trained.

3.2.1.2 Deep belief network

By stacking multiple RBMs on top of each other we can get a more powerful generative model than a single RBM called *Deep Belief Network (DBN)*. Each RBM layer is connected with the next in a directed manner. It performs a linear transformation of the previous layer's features, just like a neural network, and feeds the outputs to the next level. They too can be used in an unsupervised or supervised manner which means that they can be used to do both feature learning and classification. The training process follows a greedy layer-wise procedure where each next layer is added on top of the network and only the top layer is trained as a single RBM using contrastive divergence. The basic idea of the greedy layer-wise strategy is that after training the top-level RBM of a n-level DBN, one changes the interpretation of the RBM parameters to insert them in an (n + 1)-level DBN. Note that a 1-level DBN is actually an RBM. When the layer is trained, the weights are "frozen" and a new layer is added and the process repeats.

3.2.1.3 Stacked denoising autoencoders

An encoder is a deterministic mapping process which maps an input x to a hidden representation y usually using a nonlinear function. The same latent representation can be mapped back into a reconstruction z with another process, the decoder. By minimizing the difference between z and the initial input x the model will be forced to learn a good and robust set of features y that represent x well enough for z to be properly reconstructed. Recently Deep Neural Networks have been used as base models to make state of the art autoencoders. In such cases one feedforward network is used for dimensionality reduction and thus performs the encoding and another is used to generate data as close to the original as possible. Autoencoders can also be used to rectify faulty or noisy data by training them to ignore the types of expected noise (V., L., L., + 10).

3.3 Latent features analysis

The mixed representations of the inputs that the models learn by adjusting their inner parameters are the latent features. Basically, the models learn to combine the input features in ways that help it deal with the task at hand. For image datasets where deep learning has recently shown great achievements, a deep neural network will learn abstract visual features in a hierarchical manner such as pixel combinations that are then used to detect edges or corners which are then combined to find shapes and finally entire objects. However, on EHR datasets the input features are tabular. This means that the model can only try to make combination out of input features and estimate which of them has a clear effect on the output. Therefore,

to understand the knowledge the model has aggregated from the data, what we have to do is visualize the learned combinations that are generated during a forward pass of the model. To visually represent and evaluate the importance of the input features for a hidden node we can assign grey levels to each risk factor according to that node's gradients regarding respect to the inputs. To evaluate the risk factors quantitatively we can use the gradients with respect to the inputs to calculate the entropy of the categories of the top-k most important features for each neuron. A model having high entropy would mean that the inner neurons use features from different categories to map the inputs to the outputs and that there is a weak coherence amongst the features extracted in each neuron. In our case that would mean that features belonging to the same category (e.g physical activity) cannot be used by themselves to make clear estimations but have to be combined with various other factors. On the other hand, a model that has low categorical entropy indicates that there are groups of categories that have clear effect towards the value of the outputs.

4 Unsupervised learning in Healthcare

Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment are a central part of iHelp Platform and are closely linked with requirements that have been set in T2.1 - “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and T2.3 - “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications”.

Another dependency identified is with T3.1 - “Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records” as this task defines the common conceptual data model of iHelp - the HHRs.

During our collaboration with medical partners and other consortium members, a consensus was built that processed datasets will include in one hand incoming data from sensors, such as measurements of heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and oxygen saturation (SpO₂), number of steps etc., while on the other hand they will include periodic answers to predefined questionnaires.

This section outlines and presents some of the most used techniques for unsupervised learning in healthcare domain for anomaly detection and early risk identification that will be also adapted for addressing the iHelp goals i.e.:

- to identify hidden trends and patterns in existing data
- to identify personalised healthy targets for monitored parameters,
- to identify critical or alarming limits per user and per parameter

A larger set of data processing techniques applied in similar projects is currently provided as draft requirements, functional and non-functional specification, data models, parameters and even the use cases and scope of pilots listed as dependency are all currently in development.

The application of outlined solutions and their effectiveness largely depends on the availability of domain specific data and how those algorithms will be trained and combined.

- There are also other factors that should be taken into account for the iHelp approach of data clusterization, hidden trends and patterns detection and identification of health issues. The unsupervised learning techniques can help us with the tasks of building knowledge, research direction pre-assessment, hypothesis validation and of course for early risk identification. Furthermore, the assessment of cyclicity (periodicity) of the research should be anticipated in order to be able to make comparisons with averaged data from comparable previous periods with already known natural cyclic variations, for example: week, month, season.
- For each of those types of periods, a specific patient profile should be calculated and used for further analysis.
- Search for deviations (anomalies) from the average values for previous periods, approaching or crossing the personalised limit values or critical limits and tracking of trends in the deviations should be based primarily on comparable profiles.
- Abrupt deviations may be due to measurement errors and a mechanism for filtering them should be anticipated before data has been used for further processing and analysis.
- Potential checks for small deviations caused due to external factors, like weather conditions or stress can improve accuracy of the algorithms.

4.1 Anomaly detection

Anomaly detection is an important area in unsupervised learning that can be applied as part of the iHelp project. It will target identification and detection of pancreatic cancer-specific anomalies within datasets of healthy and affected populations in various stages of progression. As this is a rare disease the synthetic data sets described in Section 7 may be used to increase the accuracy.

At a later phase, identified factors will be used for classification of patents and users in risk profiles and identification of sudden deviations that may need instant reaction or even medical treatment.

The most promising methods applicable towards iHelp use cases and targets are:

- Decision Trees (DT): A decision tree is a flowchart-like structure in which each internal node represents a “test” on an attribute (monitored physiological attribute, here), each branch represents the outcome of the test and each leaf node represents a class label (normal or abnormal).
- Random Forests (RF): The random forest is an ensemble approach primarily based on decision tree which, in ensemble terms, corresponds to a weak learner. Random forests help by averaging multiple deep decision trees, trained on the same training set but on different parts, with the aim of reducing the variance so that there is no overfitting of training sets.
- k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN): Instance-based classifiers such as k-NN operate on the principle that unknown instances can be classified by relating the unknown to the known, according to some distance/similarity function.
- Linear and Additive Regressions.
- Decision Stump (DS): The decision stump is a ML technique which basically consists of a decision tree with one internal node (the root) which is immediately connected to the terminal nodes (its leaves).

Detailed information and comparison between all of them and their results in health care domain can be found in (P., S., 15).

The above algorithms can be adapted in the context of iHelp to allow discovery of cross dimensional connections and dependencies between different parameters, e.g., relationship between blood pressure and heart rate, such as simultaneous increase, decrease, average distance between measurements, etc.

Combining sensor and primary data with data collected via questionnaires will enable tracking the results changes, trends and personalise targets when applying diets, changes in physical activity, identify stress, etc.

Another possible direction could be the identification of connections with external events - climatic measurements, such as: temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity; magnetic storms, etc.

4.2 Time series analysis

Following techniques for health analysis of human daily physical activity based on data taken from smart watch sensor have been anticipated.

- Principal component analysis (PCA): As a dimensionality reduction algorithm, PCA is a data pre-processing method that allows shifting of m-dimensional X data to n-dimensional Y data with minimum loss.
- Random forest algorithm: Random Forest method is a classification method that is performed using a large number of tree structures instead of a single tree structure. In this method, samples from the data set are selected by Bootstrap method and classification trees are created. Using these classification trees, the observation class is decided for each tree, and the most repeated class value is selected among the classifications. The method used to create each tree in the random forest method is important in terms of determining the outcome.
- Nonstationary Distributions and Unit Roots: Unit roots can arise in multivariate time series, that is, where a vector of observations is recorded at each time point. In such cases, there may be some linear combinations of the vectors that form stationary time series and other linear combinations that are nonstationary. These results appear under the name “co-integration analysis” and “reduced rank regression”. Another possible research is “trend breaks” that can identify if one mean exists during the first period of data collection versus a second one later. This method allows determination of the break points in series and identification of cases where a seemingly nonstationary time series are in fact stationary around two or three different means.

Details about application of those algorithms in healthcare domain as well as their usage and comparison of archived results are discussed in (B., S., P., 18).

Anomaly detections in time series can also be performed by using deep learning algorithms, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) as suggested in (H., W., 20).

4.3 Artificial Intelligence techniques

The objective of unsupervised learning is to identify the inherent structure of unlabelled data. The primary goals of such unsupervised data processing are clustering, density estimation, and representation learning. AI methods applicable for processing of the results obtained by wearable devices are described in (N., A., K., + 22). For analysing data collected via wearable devices PCA and auto-encoders have been proposed and evaluated. Exploratory analysis and dimensionality reduction have been the other two common use cases used in unsupervised learning. In scenarios where the fully autonomous dataset analysis is impossible, unsupervised methods can be used to gain initial insights into the data and those insights can be used for testing different hypotheses.

4.4 Other techniques

Mental stress detection and analysis of physiological measurements like Heart Rate Variability (HRV), Electrodermal Activity (EDA), and respiration are the main subjects in (T., P., S., + 20). The article presents multiple personalized models based on an unsupervised algorithm, the Self-Organizing Map (SOM). The clusterization methods that have been outlined and compared include Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), Hidden Markov Model, K-Means and Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN). GMM and K-Means are similar partitioning methods that base the cluster structure on the distance of the observations, but GMM does not estimate the covariance structure.

Several other approaches can contribute to the achievement of the iHelp project goals:

- Data-driven Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) combined with decision-making based on distance-based detection techniques.
- Feature extraction by Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) modelling; dimensionality reduction by a deep autoencoder; and feature classification via the Mahalanobis distance metric.

A combination of Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), a MLP model, a LSTM model, and an ensemble model combining predictions of the ARIMA, MLP, and LSTM models calibrated to predict the expenditures on different medications.

5 Survival estimation

Survival estimation also known as time-to-event analysis is the estimation of the time between an exposure and an event. Relevant data is modelled either in terms of the probability that an individual survives past a certain point in time (survival functions) or in terms of the probability of having an event at a certain time (hazard functions). In the case of the project, it could be the time between diagnosis and passing away or healing of the patient. There are generally nonparametric-parametric models that yield results for the entire population and models that take patient characteristics into consideration when performing the estimation.

5.1 Non-Personalized

The simplest survival estimation technique is the **Kaplan Meier** estimator (G., K., K., 18). It basically estimates a single survival estimation curve for an entire population using only one feature: individual survival times. The resulting curve cannot give a personalized estimate of the survival of a patient, but it can be used as a baseline technique or a tool to study different subsets of populations.

$$S(t_i) = S(t_{i-1}) \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{n_i}\right)$$

- $S(t_{i-1})$: the probability of being alive at t_{i-1}
- n_i : number of alive patients before t_i
- d_i : number of events at time t_i
- $t_0 = 0, S(0) = 1$

5.2 Personalized

As mentioned above the Kaplan-Meier technique describes the survival of a person using a univariate approach which does not allow for personal estimations. The simplest technique that addresses this issue is **Cox proportional hazards** model (G., K., K., 18). This technique aims to evaluate simultaneously the effect of survival times with other factors. It does so by calculating the baseline hazard function and multiplying it by the individual's hazard ratios as seen in the formula below.

$$h(t) = h_0(t)e^{\sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i}$$

- $h(t)$: the hazard function with covariates x_i as inputs
- the effect of the covariates x_i is measured by the coefficients b_i
- h_0 : baseline hazard, determined by the entire population

These hazard ratios use the results of a multiple linear regression that estimates the risk level of a patient to estimate the patient's individual hazard function proportionally to their risk level. The survival function can then be estimated with regards to the person's hazard function.

Instead of using a logistic regression to amplify a basic survival function that is derived from the entire population, nonlinear functions can be used to estimate the survival functions for subpopulations. The simplest algorithm is the Survival Tree where a Decision Tree is used to split the population into different groups and a baseline hazard function is calculated for each of these subsets of the initial population. The patient's survival function is then determined by their personal risk score combined with the baseline function of the subgroup they were categorized to by the decision tree.

This allows the model to split higher and lower risks of population so that an individual's survival function is based on patients with more similar characteristics to them as well as their own characteristics. Extending that concept other classifiers may be used instead of a Decision Tree such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting or even deep neural networks like in the case of DeepSurv for even better classification.

$$h(t) = h_i(t)e^{\sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i}$$

- $h(t)$: the hazard function with covariates x_i as inputs
- the effect of the covariates x_i is measured by the coefficients b_i
- h_i : baseline hazard for the specific class, determined by the classification algorithm

Another group of techniques focuses on utilizing unsupervised learning by performing clustering (e.g., K Means or hierarchical clustering) of the patients based on risk profiles. By trying to find subgroups of population in the feature space instead of using classifiers they base the time to event predictions on groups with similar characteristics.

In the earlier Cox regression models, it was assumed that patient's covariates are constant across time. However, in our project variables values will change through time (especially for secondary data). For this purpose, it is important to be able to handle time varying data. It is possible to handle such cases by modifying the Cox Proportional Hazard (CoxPH) model by extending the dataset with start-stop format to denote the time boundaries for which the covariates had each specific set of values. Then the time varying CoxPH algorithm makes the estimation of the hazard ratios by considering only the relevant time periods for each feature combination and event occurrence. This way the changes that have happened to the features during the trial are accounted for when estimating the changes in target features and predictions.

6 Application on synthetic data

In the previous chapters, various algorithms for prediction and risk assessment have been outlined. None of them is applied to data collected in iHelp, since the studies that will provide the iHelp datasets have not yet started. In the absence of iHelp data at this phase, in this chapter we present a workflow for the learning of predictive and generative models on synthetic data. This is data provided by a simulator, and although the behavioural attributes to be collected in iHelp will be quite similar, there is no claim that the attribute values, prediction outcomes and groups of simulated people have any clinical resemblance with cancer patients. In the following sections we will briefly present the simulator that provides synthetic data, followed by specific examples of learning on the synthesized data, both for predictive and for generative models.

6.1 Simulation for synthetic data

While at this stage of the iHelp project there exist primary (clinical) retrospective data, there are no secondary (Real-world/behavioural) data, especially correlated with the primary, nor of a longitudinal (across time) nature. In the absence of such data, and in anticipation of the data to be collected in the iHelp clinical studies, we have built a Real-World Data (RWD) Simulator (P., K., M., 21) that can provide synthetic data to be used when building and testing our model learning and inference pipelines.

The RWD simulator accepts demographic and behavioural information of the simulated people/individuals and simulates days of their lives. This input information forms the behavioural phenotypes. The demographic information includes gender, date of birth, height, weight, health status, employment, and country of residence. The behavioural phenotypes enumerate the tendency of the people towards activities related to six behavioural traits: indoor and outdoor entertainment, indoor and outdoor athletics, inactivity, and work. For the purpose of the data synthesis for the early iHelp learning experiments we have defined the four behavioural phenotypes of Table 1. The actual behaviours are obtained by Gaussian dithering of these values with a small standard deviation.

Table 1: The four behavioural phenotypes of the early iHelp experiments in terms of the six behavioural traits of the simulator.

Behaviour	Health	Outdoor athletic	Indoor athletic	Outdoor entertainment	Indoor entertainment	Bed lover	Work-acholic
Athletic	[80, 90]	30	25	10	5	25	5
Normal	[60, 70]	20	15	15	15	20	15
Unfit	[40, 50]	5	10	20	25	15	25
Feeble	[20, 30]	5	5	10	50	10	20

Groups of activities are defined for each of the six behavioural traits. For example, outdoor athletic activities include walking, hiking, running and bicycle riding. Every time the simulated person is about to select a new activity, they refer to their assigned behavioural trait to select the next activity group. The selection is non-deterministic, but the chances of each activity group are weighted by the personality, the time of day and the recent history of activity selection. Once the activity group is selected, an activity within the group is

chosen randomly. The duration of the activity is chosen based on a Gaussian duration model that each activity has, and the remaining stamina of the person.

The duration of the activity is simulated in small time steps, the simulator time delta, which defaults to five minutes. For every simulation time delta, each activity generates values for each Real-World Data (RWD) measurement by defining models of the measurement x as:

$$x = \begin{cases} 0 & u < T \\ N(m, \sigma^2 | a) & u \geq T \end{cases}$$

where u is a random variable uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$, T is a threshold value in $[0, 1]$ that depends on the activity a , and $N(m, \sigma^2 | a)$ is a Gaussian random variable of mean m and variance σ^2 that also depend on the activity a . The mean m also depends on the available stamina of the simulated person. The threshold T is usually zero, resulting in values drawn from the Gaussian distribution. It is close to unity for activities wherein some non-zero measurements can appear sporadically, such as non-zero steps while working or sleeping, or floor climbing while walking.

Most activities diminish the stamina of the people, i.e., the available pool of energy to keep doing high-intensity activities. Some leisure activities do replenish stamina though, but it is mainly sleep that does the trick. The level of replenishment depends on the person's health and quality of sleep.

Care is taken to respect weekends and vacations based on the country of residence of each person, whereupon work is eliminated (unless there is a strong work behavioural trait). There are random events that temporarily affect the health of people (illnesses and accidents, even mood-related events). Their probability increases as health is reduced. Health is reduced constantly by age, but it is also affected by long-term behaviour; weight gain and lack of exercise or quality sleep will, in the long run, reduce health. The opposite behaviour will improve health.

The simulated RWD are complemented with reports from questionnaires. Every question is defined, together with a model that determines the answer the simulator should give. The model equations are defined using any of the data produced by the simulator (either measurements or reports), including their short- and long-term averages and trends. For example, the answer to the "ability to perform the usual activities" question is modelled with a mean value of:

$$(100 - \{HEALTH_SHORT\}) / 20 + \{PAIN_SHORT\} + \{HEADACHE_SHORT\} - \{MOOD_SHORT\} + 2$$

and a constant standard deviation of 0.5. Similarly, the answer to the mobility ability question is modelled with a mean value of

$$5 - \exp(\{STEPS\} / 3000)$$

and the same constant standard deviation. In the above expressions HEALTH_SHORT, PAIN_SHORT, HEADACHE_SHORT and MOOD_SHORT refer to the short-term averages of the equivalent symptom, and STEPS refers to the total steps walked in that day.

The RWD simulator is implemented in Python and generates RWD for every delta time interval. It also stores all simulated physical exercise sessions and all answers to questionnaires. The generated data are stored into CSV files containing the dynamic info, i.e., the RWD for all time delta intervals, the daily aggregations of all generated RWD and the answers to questionnaires, as well as the static info of the participants (the behaviours). It requires 80ms on average to simulate a person-day on a seventh generation Intel i7 CPU.

The simulator has been employed to generate 114 weeks of data for 2,000 people of all behaviours shown in Table 1.

6.2 Predictive modelling

In this section we learn and analyse a predictive model, as an example of supervised learning. We first define the learning experiment in terms of input attributes and outcome to predict. We then train a Random Forest (RF) predictor. Then we discuss the important attributes in the model inferences employing SHAP (Shapley Additive exPlanations) analysis. The section concludes with a proposal for risk assessment, based on accumulating the decisions on the simulated individuals across time.

6.2.1 Inputs and outcomes to predict

The RWD simulator has generated many daily vectors each consisting of a multitude of attributes. Every day the people assess their health outlook by answering a related questionnaire. We want to predict the health outlook variation between the assessment to be made in the beginning of the week, based on the assessment of the beginning of the previous week and all data accumulated about the person in this week. The accumulated data are represented by the short-term (weekly) averages of the different attributes, as well as their trends, i.e., the normalised variation of the weekly averages from the long-term (quarterly) averages.

We selected a subset of the attributes as inputs. These are:

- The steps walked, calories burned, *sleep quality*, *body mass index*, *mood reported* and *water consumption* (short-term averages and trends – 12 attributes)
- The health outlook self-assessment of the previous week in the five-level scale used in the related question (short-term average and trend – 2 attributes)
- The *age* (static info – 1 attribute)

In total, there are 15 input attributes.

The outcome to predict is the binary-quantized version of the weekly health outlook variation: Is the person perceiving an improvement of their health, or a worsening after the week they just had?

In total there are 114 (weeks) times, 2,000 (people) weekly vectors of 15 input attributes and one outcome to work with. They are split into training (60% of the people), validation (20%) and testing (20%) sets.

6.2.2 RF predictive model

A Random Forest classifier is learned on the training data, using the validation data for hyperparameter tuning. The choice for a Random Forest classifier is based on the fact that seldom a single study can accumulate the number of data points to train a Neural Network of any significant depth. So even if the synthetic data at hand have the necessary volume, we chose the algorithm that will most probably fit the data we will actually have. The balanced accuracy of the prediction is shown in Figure 7, where the hyperparameter tuned in the number of estimators (trees) in the Random Forest. The achieved validation and testing accuracies, as well as the confusion matrix are also shown for the best RF learned.

Figure 7: Learning of the RF binary health outlook variation classifier.

Working on the train and validation sets is done in the model learning workflow. The inference workflow utilises the testing set. Since the testing accuracy is even higher than the validation, and we have not retrained our model including the validation set after hyperparameter tuning, in the rest of the inference results shown in the following sub-sections we have merged the validation and testing sets.

6.2.3 Explaining model decisions

The derivation of the attributes that are most influential towards positive or negative outcomes per person in a short time interval is important for the iHelp virtual coaching service. To do so, a second part of the inference workflow involves explaining the decisions. We employ SHAP analysis of the decisions which yield the importance of the different attributes on the decisions. The results are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: SHAP analysis of decisions.

As can be seen from Figure 8, across all four simulated behaviours, the most important attribute is the BMI trend, followed by the short-term averages of the steps walked and the calories burned. Similarly, the trend

of the water consumption is the least important attribute, followed by the short-term average of the water consumption, the age and the sleep quality trend.

6.2.4 Risk assessment

Risk assessment using model decisions is very important for iHelp. In this particular example, we provide well-being assessment as the accumulation of the decisions across time. This assessment ranges from -1 (extreme risk) to +1 (zero risk – perfect well-being outlook). Please note that the well-being assessment (W) can be transformed into a risk assessment (R) by negating, shifting, and scaling as follows:

$$R = \frac{1 - W}{2}$$

Figure 9 depicts the histograms of the well-being assessment for each of the four behaviours. While the feeble and unfit histograms are quite distinct from any of the normal or athletic ones, the latter two are quite overlapping, indicating that positive health assessments can be obtained not only for people of athletic disposition, but also normal people who exercise somewhat. Nonetheless, the average well-being assessments are quite distinct, and the Bhattacharyya coefficients of every histogram pair are quite acceptably small.

Figure 9: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the behaviour group of each person.

6.3 Generative modelling

Meaningful clusters of patients are useful to have in iHelp. The usefulness refers to the existence of common characteristics in these clusters, like common inference results or matching of these clusters to known patient behaviours. In this section we learn generative models as an example of unsupervised learning. We do so by clustering the patients into groups and modelling each of the groups. Then we assign patients to the different groups, and attempt to characterize the group importance, promoting useful

groups into phenotypes. The process is depicted in Figure 10, and its elements are detailed in the following sub-sections.

Figure 10: Cluster analysis process.

6.3.1 Pre-processing

There are different pre-processing options to be explored (by applying them prior to clustering the data) and then validated, considering the resulting clusters. The first option explored was attribute selection which involves the selection of some attributes out of the full set to work upon. The selection can be based on the correlation of the attributes with some clinical outcome of interest. Most clustering algorithms need the data at hand to be standardized or normalized. For both processes, the attributes are rescaled. Standardization is achieved by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation, making them zero and unit respectively and normalization by making the attributes have a similar scale that has a range [0,1] or [-1,1]. The aim of rescaling the data is for features to have a common scale without distorting the differences (P., F., 14). Since some attributes can be considered more important than others, they can be re-scaled to violate the normalization process, causing them to have a larger effect on the computed distances at the heart of the clustering algorithm. Important attributes to keep or scale can be identified via correlation analysis with some outcome of interest. A reduction of dimensionality can be performed using either the t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE) or the principal component analysis (PCA) algorithm. T-SNE is a non-linear transformation that gives each data point a location in 2-dimensions. This algorithm is very flexible and preserves only local similarities. To measure the pairwise similarities this algorithm uses a student t-distribution (M., H., 08). PCA preserves large distances and maximizes the variance and then it uses this to define the new basis. Large variance is interesting and wanted as it corresponds to dynamics in the system. When a percentage variance is chosen, the PCA will determine the number of components (dimensions) from the input data so that they have this percentage of variability (S., H., 19).

6.3.2 Clustering

The attributes forming the input vectors to be clustered are those of the predictive modelling, appending to it the prediction outcome, resulting to vectors of 16 attributes. We selected the hierarchical clustering algorithm to derive the clusters of patients. This algorithm clusters similar data points using dendrograms. The tree is built by an agglomerative (bottom-up) approach where the root is a cluster with all the samples and the leaves are clusters with only one sample. Then, pairs of clusters are merged while moving up the hierarchy using Euclidean distance as a metric to decide which clusters should be combined. In addition, a

Ward linkage criterion is used which minimizes the variance of the clusters being merged¹. After the tree is built it must be pruned, i.e., reduced by removing non-critical sections, at the maximum tolerated distance or at the wanted number of clusters. The tree is pruned at a maximum tolerated distance of 100, resulting to 9 clusters, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Hierarchical clustering of the people.

6.3.3 Modelling clusters

Each of the clusters has its attributes modelled using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM). The process of training GMM is achieved by using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm. This algorithm has two steps: the E-step where an initial guess is made on the parameters and the M-step where the algorithm updates the parameters. These steps are repeated until they converge². We optimize the number of Gaussians via Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) minimization. This criterion is a measurement that can predict the error of a statistical model. It was found that for the best quality of the model large number of Gaussians is needed. Our data is high-dimensional and many attributes are discrete. Therefore, we need to extend the number of vectors to dither the discrete values and allow modelling with a high number of Gaussians.

The resulting GMM models for the 16 attributes (rows) and the nine clusters (columns) are depicted in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

6.3.4 Assigning patients to clusters (phenotyping)

Phenotyping is a process where we assign each patient to a model, i.e., the GMM representing a cluster. To assign a patient to a phenotype we consider all the vectors including their measurements for a time period. Then the probability of every vector being modelled by each model is calculated and the model from which results in the highest probability is selected. The selections are aggregated in the time period of interest.

¹ SciKit. Clustering: 2.3.6. Hierarchical clustering [Internet]. Available from: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/clustering.html#hierarchical-clustering>

² Glen S. EM Algorithm (Expectation-maximization): Simple Definition [Internet]. StatisticsHowTo.com. Available from: <https://www.statisticshowto.com/em-algorithm-expectation-maximization/>

6.3.5 Cluster validation

Figure 12: Models for the first half attributes of all 9 clusters.

The obtained clusters can be validated into data-driven phenotypes of the people. The obtained clusters should include people from one of the behaviours. The behaviour-based groups (or any other clinicians' classification) and data-driven clusters can be compared, e.g., see Figure 14. In this example clusters 1, 2, and 3 can be easily assigned to one outcome, while clusters 4, 5, and 6 could have 2 possible outcomes, and finally cluster 7 is problematic.

Quantitatively, the process of calculating the validity of the clusters is as follows:

- Cluster c has $N(c)$ members. Most of the members should exhibit a single outcome, and very few should exhibit different outcomes
- Each of the members exhibits an outcome o . The count of the different outcomes is $n(c, o)$. One of the outcomes, h has the highest count, $n(c, h)$, $h = \operatorname{argmax}(n(c, o))$
- From the $N(c)$ members of cluster c , the majority $n(c, o)$ belong to the same outcome o
- The score $s(c)$ is defined as $\frac{n(c, h)}{N(c)}$, which is then normalized by the worst-case score of having all outcomes equally represented in the cluster
- Overall, the score s of all clusters is the normalized weighted sum of the individual scores: $\sum(N(c) * s(c)) / \sum N(c)$, where the sums are performed across all clusters

- A penalty of $\log_2(\text{No of clusters})$ is applied, since elsehow the maximum cluster cleanness is guaranteed when each vector forms its own cluster

Figure 13: Models for the second half attributes of all 9 clusters.

Figure 14: Comparison between data-driven clusters and behavioural clusters (clinicians’ classification).

The data driven cluster validation process is shown in Figure 13, where the rows correspond to the nine clusters. The first column contains a human-readable ID for the cluster. The next 4 columns contain the number of people in the given cluster (row) coming from each of the behavioural groups (columns). The

clusters are scored (6th column) based on how many people in it do not correspond to the predominant behavioural group, thus each row should have a single non-zero entry in columns 2 to 5 for a cluster score of 100. The final column shows the percentage of the population attributed to the corresponding cluster.

Table 2: Validating clusters into data-driven phenotypes based on behavioural group matching.

PHENOTYPE	FEEBLE	UNFIT	NORMAL	ATHLETIC	SCORE	PERCENTAGE
UNFIT	2	70	11	0	84.34	20.39
FEEBLE	85	15	0	0	85.00	24.57
NORMAL-ATHLETIC	0	1	22	16	56.41	9.58
NORMAL	0	2	34	6	80.95	10.32
UNFIT (2)	1	3	0	0	75.00	0.98
NORMAL (2)	0	0	1	0	100.00	0.25
UNFIT (3)	1	24	0	0	96.00	6.14
ATHLETIC-NORMAL	0	0	12	15	55.56	6.63
ATHLETIC	0	0	13	73	84.88	21.13

The weighted score of all clusters is 65.8%, mainly because well-being assessments overlap across neighbouring behavioural phenotypes. Please note that two neighbouring non-zero entries are to be expected, especially for the normal and athletic behavioural groups whose well-being assessments have a significant overlap. Hence it should not be a surprise that two of the phenotypes are quite balanced mixtures of the normal and athletic behaviours. Clusters with high scores and significant percentages of appearance in the population are validated into data-driven phenotypes. Note that the description of these phenotypes in terms of the included behaviours are listed in the first column.

Finally, the well-being assessments of people are revisited in Figure 15, this time from the cluster viewpoint. The histograms conditioned upon the cluster are in most cases distinct, showing how well-being assessment can be expected from the cluster of the person.

Figure 15: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the cluster of each person.

7 Initial architecture and connection to the pilot studies

In the second year of the project more information (periodicity of delivery, features, clearer plan for the desired outcomes) about the secondary, the streaming and genomic data were provided by the responsible partners (clinicians, etc.). Moreover, some synthetic data were also available and hence we were able to initialize the design of the architecture and develop early AI models that will be used in the third year of the project on the availability of the actual aforementioned data. In particular, a description of the data is provided followed by the workflow of the predicted models and the connection to other WPs and tasks. Finally, an initial approach of the AI models' architecture is presented taking into account the data provided so far. This section will be extended in the next and final version of D4.3 - "Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment III" with specific sections that will be related to every pilot taking into consideration the specific predictions related to each pilot.

7.1 Data description

The T5.1 - "Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment" will extend the AI models produced under T4.1 - "Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions" of WP4 by incorporating other types of data apart from the clinical retrospective data provided in T4.1 - "Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions". The idea in T5.1 - "Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment" is to perform continuous risk assessment and for its realization, prospective clinical data will also be collected. The prospective clinical data consist of:

- phenotypic data: are all kinds of clinical information regarding patients' disease symptoms, as well as relevant demographic data, such as age, ethnicity and sex.
- blood exams (e.g., hemoglobin to detect anemia)
- disease specific data

In addition, the HDM pilot will provide epigenetics throughout the trials' duration. Epigenetics is the study of how your behaviors and environment can cause changes that affect the way genes work. Unlike genetic changes, epigenetic changes are reversible and do not change the DNA sequence, but they can change how your body reads a DNA sequence. Explained in a very basic way, what we are willing to explore are some methylation indexes for the same patients in two moments of time, at the beginning and at the end of the trials, to observe how the change in life habits may reduce those indexes. The key point here is that omics analytics is an intrusive type of analysis that quite often introduces "batch effects" to the extent that samples analysed in different processes may turn even incomparable. To avoid this, we planned to obtain the samples at the beginning of the pilot, freeze them, obtain samples again at the end of the pilot and perform the analytics jointly, in the same process. That way, the possible batch effect would affect all the samples and keep them still comparable.

Finally, yet importantly, streaming data is another source of information that can assist the continuous risk assessment. The streaming data consists of:

- life habit data questionnaires (e.g., smoking)
- symptoms related questionnaires: which will be answered by the patients during the trials
- medical sensor data collected through wearable devices (e.g., heartbeat rate).

More details about the streaming data can be found in the thorough analysis of Section 6.

7.2 Predictive workflow

The model developed in this task aims to complement the model developed in T4.1 – “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” where the goal is to provide risk prediction based on retrospective clinical data. Based on the bibliography, clinical data are not enough to make a decision, so by adding streaming data, models may acquire a better perception of the patient and a continuous risk assessment can be applied that could allow achieving a potential early risk identification. In Figure 16 the predictive workflow is depicted taking into account the work done under T4.1 – “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” but also the work under T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”.

In the implemented AI models, provided in T4.1 – “Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions” (Model 1), labels are assigned to the patients based on retrospective data both clinical and genomic data (where available). Our intention to incorporate also the data described in sub-Section 7.1, is to begin with the new clinical data once it becomes available and feed it to model 1 which in turn will take into consideration the initial genomic data but also the new clinical data to re-assess the condition in which the patient will be. The silver labels produced from Model 1 will then be used as an input in Model 2. In the training phase, Model 2 is taking as input streaming data along with the current clinical data and each time a new clinical trial takes place the new data will be ingested into the model. Model 2 will be able to provide predictions by considering the clinical data provided at a specific time instance (e.g., the third red vertical line in Figure 16) with the streaming data provided at the same time window (black vertical lines inside the yellow box in Figure 16). This time window could refer, for instance, to the streaming data collected in the last 3 months.

Figure 16: The process of the collection of data and the models accompanying them

7.3 Model architecture

The AI model of T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment” is envisioned as a NN that concatenates multiple sub-neural networks since it will extend the work done under T4.1 –

“Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions”. In particular, each sub-neural network as it will be trained under specific data, will be able to process diverse information and transfer the knowledge into other layers of the unified NN. Each time, the series dataset will be processed in different models i.e., sub-NN. More specifically, there are a couple of time series AI models available, an LSTM and a CNN. As an example, let’s assume that clinical data (DB1) arrive every month, the dataset of questionnaires is updated (DB2) on weekly basis and the streaming IoT data (DB3) are provided on daily basis. Therefore, the model will incorporate two-time series models, one for each streaming dataset of DB2 and DB3 to accompany the model which processes DB1. The time series model of DB2 takes as input a dataset with size:

[number of patients * (number of observations * number of features)].

In the following example, the size of DB2 array is (3, 4, 2), the DB3 has a size of (3, 30, 2), where 30 are the days of a month as this dataset will be updated daily by the patients.

Table 3. Example of DB2 with 3 patients, each questionnaire is sent per week basis by the patient, and they fill in two questions giving grades (questions are a, b):

ID	Dates	a	b
01	02/04	10	15
	09/04	20	25
	16/04	20	25
	23/04	10	35
02	07/04	99	25
	14/04	80	35
	21/04	80	35
	28/04	90	45
03	04/04	98	25
	11/04	88	35
	18/04	80	35
	25/04	90	45

Putting all together, the unified model will concatenate CNN/LSTM for each streaming data and a MLP for phenotype + blood exams + disease specific data (see Figure 17 and Figure 18 for details on the several layers).

Figure 17: Neural network that concatenates CNN/LSTM for streaming data and a simple MLP for clinical and retrospective data

Two different time series models can be applied as each of them has certain advantages. On the one hand, CNN learns a good representation of the features, while LSTM takes into consideration the history of streaming data while it does not need constraints on the number of the features like CNNs.

Figure 18: Neural network that concatenates multiple sub neural networks

Figure 18 depicts the internal architecture of the proposed convolutional Neural Network (CNN), which is a Deep Learning algorithm. The pre-processing required in a CNN is significant lower as compared to other classification algorithms where instead of applying hand-engineered techniques, with enough training CNNs have the ability to learn these characteristics by its own. It is important to mention that a CNN is able to successfully capture any temporal dependencies between successive iterations of life habit questionnaires or medical streaming data, collected regularly from the patients. The objective of the convolution layer, shown in Figure 18, is to identify high-level features. The pooling layer that follows right after is responsible to reduce the size of features computed by the convolution layer and its role is twofold: in principle, it applies dimensionality reduction on the convolved features and can also help identifying dominant features among them. Max pooling actually returns the maximum value from the time series-

based inputs while at the same time helps reducing any noise in the input data. Finally, a fully connected layer is added on top of the previous layers that is responsible to learn any non-linear combinations from the high-level input features so that it can then reveal any possible hidden patterns. At the end, the model will be able to distinguish between the dominating/important and the low-level features and classify them among the three risk levels (low, moderate and high) using the Softmax classification technique. A Softmax classifier is simply a generalization of the binary form of LR classifier.

8 Conclusion

This report aims at identifying the baseline for the techniques to be utilized towards early risk identification for pancreatic cancer. To this end, in this document a thorough bibliographic review of the state-of-the-art AI/ML techniques and algorithms for early risk identification predictions and assessment were presented. Due to lack of real data at this stage of the project we have been researching in the related literature, and in this report, we have included the tools we identified as the most suitable that we intend to use in the next phase of the project. It is clear that the literature is not extensive when it comes to AI/ML for PC, nevertheless there are many methods that could be utilized as a baseline for early risk identification and predictions. The first version of this series of deliverables, i.e., D5.1 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I”, was used as a guide for the techniques that we will possibly use as a baseline. This second version, i.e., D5.2 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment II”, provides an update on synthetic data - already available - that simulate the real data that will be provided in the last phase of the project. Furthermore, this version establishes the architecture of the AI models taking into account the synthetic data but also the several types of data that are expected in the final phase of the project. Given that in the final phase of the project relevant data will have been collected, thus the next and final version of the current report (i.e., D5.3 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment III”) will report on the specific techniques and their implementations utilized for the project datasets.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
ARMA	Autoregressive Moving Average
ATC	Athens Technology Centre
BMI	Body Mass Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CoxPH	Cox Proportional Hazard
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DBN	Deep Belief Network
DBP	Diastolic Blood Pressure
DL	Deep Learning
DS	Decision Stump
DT	Decision Trees
EDA	Electrodermal Activity
EGE	European Group on Ethics
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Models
HDBSCAN	Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
HHR	Holistic Health Records
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
HR	Heart Rate
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
iSPRINT	Innovation Sprint
KI	Karolinska Institutet
KM	K-Means
k-NN	k- Nearest Neighbours
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LXS	LeanXcale
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
NN	Neural Network
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
PDAC	Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma
RBM	Restricted Boltzmann Machine
RNNs	Recurrent Neural Networks
RF	Random Forest

RWD	Real-World Data
SBP	Systolic Blood Pressure
SHAP	Shapley Additive exPlanations
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIE	Siemens
SOM	Self-Organizing Map
SVM	Support Vector Machine
UN	United Nations
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre

Annex I: Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI

This task also checks the applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (issued by the EC on 8 April 2019) and provides a report in the relevant deliverables i.e., D5.1 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I”, D5.2 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment II” and D5.3 – “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment III”.

Among others, iHelp will produce AI based techniques and algorithms to enable early identification of Pancreatic Cancer. Under T5.1 – “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, these algorithms aim to reveal hidden patterns and trends in real-time/prospective data, in order to make predictions and also perform assessment of relevant identified risks. More specifically, the goal is to develop data analytic techniques to enable early risk identification, assessment and mitigation of measures, through the development of personalized models. As mentioned in previous chapters, the use of frugal AI techniques will enable the assessment of different clinical symptoms in relation with data coming from lifestyle, nutrition, physical activity, environmental and in general – as it is defined in iHelp - ‘secondary data’. Due to the indisputable correlation of the implementation of AI techniques and the work under this Task (and this WP), the examination of the applicability of the ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI, is more than valuable.

As stated in the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI” document, written by the High – Level Expert Group on AI (HLEG) on April 2019, Trustworthy AI is based on three pillars (T., L., S., 21). Each one separately, should be met throughout the whole system’s life cycle. The first one refers to the lawful obedience of the system, including compliance with regulations. The legal sources include the EU primary and secondary law, the UN Human Rights treaties, and the Council of Europe conventions, as well as numerous EU Member State laws. The second pillar refers to the ethical perspective, including compliance with ethical principles and values. Under that scope, the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) proposed 9 basic principles.

Four of the ethical principles/ ethical imperatives that have derived from the proposed ones, are: a) respect for human autonomy, b) Prevention of harm, c) Fairness and c) Explicability. Among others, the “ethical for human autonomy” principle includes the securing of human oversight over work processes in AI systems. More specifically, AI systems should not unjustifiably subordinate, coerce, deceive, manipulate, condition or herd humans. Regarding the ‘prevention of harm’ principle, it entails the protection of human dignity, mental and physical integrity, as well as the protection of natural environment and all living beings. Moreover, the ‘principle of fairness’ refers to both the sustainable and procedural dimension, meaning commitment to ensuring equal distribution of benefits and costs, as well as equal opportunities in terms of education, goods and services. Finally, the “principle of explicability” refers to the transparency and “explainability” of the information of who is/will be affected directly or indirectly. Finally, the third pillar is based on the robustness in terms of technical and social perspective. Under T5.1 of the iHelp project, all the AI algorithms that will be developed should comply with all pillars of the Ethics Guidelines. During the development, deployment and use of the AI algorithms specific ethical principles should be respected as declared in D1.3 “Periodic Management Report I”.